

THE OR FOUNDATION

TO: The Clerk of Committee
Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs
Office of Parliament
Osu – Accra

FROM: The OR Foundation LBG
Registered Ghanaian Charity [REDACTED]

DATE: September 29th, 2021

RE: Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021

Esteemed Members,

Please receive this memorandum as a record of our extreme concern about the negative ramifications of the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill. As a charity organization working with vulnerable populations in Ghana we are opposed to this bill in the strongest possible way. If enacted, the bill will have disastrous consequences for Human Rights and for Ghana's economy.

Fundamentally the bill openly and systematically discriminates against members of the LGBTQ community, denying basic freedoms of expression and subjecting Ghanaians at large to undue scrutiny from law enforcement authorities and from friends and neighbors alike. In so doing the bill runs counter to principles of freedom and justice on which the nation was founded. Under the proposed legislation, writing this letter would be illegal.

Within the discriminatory framework of the bill is a dangerous path toward a police state, where the act of existing is in itself a crime. We fear that this would irrevocably change the social fabric of Ghana.

Outside of Ghana the bill jeopardizes the nation's standing in global affairs and in so doing will roll back the great progress Ghana has made economically and culturally on the world stage. Already countless protests have occurred outside Ghanaian embassies around the world led by diasporans standing firmly against the bill. The image of Ghana as a welcoming nation has already suffered as a result of the introduction of the bill in Ghana's parliament. The passage of the bill will reverse the hard work of the Ghana Tourism Authority in attracting positive attention from around the world.

Most notably the UN Human Rights Council along with the UN Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights have condemned the bill and called on your committee to reject it. The UN report released in August after a thorough analysis conducted by UN Human Rights experts declares that the bill grossly violates basic Human Rights and international treaties, such as the absolute prohibition on torture. The UN has further stated that if enacted the bill is a textbook example of discrimination and amounts to State-sponsored violence, further noting that the draft legislation runs counter to Ghana's impressive record of progress toward certain Millineum Development Goals. In addition the Speaker of Parliament for ECOWAS has echoed the severe concerns of the UN Human Rights

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Council. As an organization engaged in supporting marginalized communities we join other groups such as Amnesty International and Human Rights Watch in fervently supporting the United Nations' interpretation of the bill as having no place in a democratic state.

Given the clear violations of basic Human Rights the proposed legislation would also violate the Human Rights provisions in international trade agreements, chief among them the African Growth and Opportunities Act (AGOA), which provides tariff incentives for exports to the United States of America. This would have a devastating negative economic impact for the country, causing losses to Ghanaian businesses of USD \$720 Million annually, which is the value of goods from Ghana that would lose preferential access to the American market should the bill be enacted. AGOA clearly stipulates that a nation is only qualified for preferential tariff status if the nation "does not engage in gross violations of internationally recognised human rights." (Section 104 (A) 3) Considering the definitive analysis from the United Nations that describes the proposed law as a gross violation of basic Human Rights, the passage of this bill would trigger the suspension of Ghana's access to the AGOA agreement according to the language within Section 104 of the AGOA agreement. The proposed bill also threatens international loan agreements and aid packages with organizations such as the World Bank Group and USAID, among other major lending and donor institutions with Human Rights-based program requirements.

It is important to contextualize this bill within global movements. Language in the bill is a carbon copy of language used by the World Congress of Families, a group which over ten years ago worked with members of the Parliament of Uganda to pass a similar discriminatory bill. The Ugandan law was overturned after the United States of America implemented sanctions, including travel restrictions, cancelled military support, and threatened to revoke Uganda's participation in the African Growth and Opportunities Act along with rescinding a US \$125 Million aid package. The World Congress of Families is classified by the Southern Poverty Law Center as a hate group, the strongest term of condemnation for groups intending to inflict harm based on race, ethnicity, gender or sexual orientation. Adopting this bill would make Ghana's parliament appear to also be a hate group.

Rejecting the bill is the only way to stand for the principles of dignity, privacy and freedom enshrined in Ghana's constitution. As an organization with the idea of choice in our name ("or") this is not the Ghana we choose and we sincerely hope that it is not the Ghana you choose either.

Faithfully,

The OR Foundation team